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ECONOMY OF CHATRAPATI SHIVAJI'S TIME

Research paper in History

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Introduction:-

Chatrapati Shivaji Maharaj was born on Feb19, 1630 at Shivneri Castle. Duration of Shivkal includes Chatrapati Shahaji Raje, Chatrapati ShavajiRaje, Chatrapati Sambhaji Raje, Chatrapati Rajaram and Tarabai. To understand the contemporary Economy, Business, Industrialization and Farming. It needs to refer the contemporary reference books, Bakhars, official Letters, etc.

To keep the transparency in the state management and economy management, Shaivaji Raje had established 'Ashtpradhan' committee. In this 'Ashtpradhan' Committee 'Amatya' plays vital role in relation to economy management 'Amatya' kept management of kingdom's income and expenditure. Amatya conformed and managed the economy budget. Farming was main source of income of subject and kingdom. Kingdom got income through agricultural taxes.

Research Methodology:-

In the present research paper, one has presented economy of Chatrapati Shivaji's Time. The sources of the study for this paper are reference books, periodicals, news papers, and short notes of subject experts lectures.

Objectives of research paper:-

1. A study of income sources during Shivkal economy system.
2. A study of currency management during Shivkal
3. Shivkaline Economy policy and its use for present.

Hypothesis:-

1. Chatrapati Shivaji Raje was skillful economist.
2. Chatrapati Shivaji Raje established kingdom for subject welfare.

Sources of Income during Shivkal :-

Agricultural tax is main source of income during that contemporary period. Other sources are tax, gifts from other kings, presents, chatunai, etc are important sources. The agricultural tax was depends on the annual income of formers. It is 2/5 out of total income. This tax was only implacable for fertile farming only .During the period of Shivkal, people were appointed in different period. In 1636, Dadoji Kondev , in 1648 Moro Pingale and in 1678 , Annaji Dattoji were appointed as tax officers to collect agricultural tax. Chatrapati Shivaji was self interested in farming he was personally concentrated on farming and tried to developed agricultural income. He was first conscious king (Janta Raja) He decided to give loan for agricultural development. He made strict rules for military, who did not destroy the crop of farmers. At that time there were taxes on gift contrition (Inapatti), tax contributed from gold smith (sarafpatti), loyalty tax (Miras tax) miras patmti, tax on oil (Tel Patti), tax on shepherds (Dhangarpatti). There were some occasional taxes like Shinhasan tax and Takhta tax.

Agriculture Policy :-

Shivaji Maharaj had made following three special policies for agriculture –

1. Unfertile land makes fertile.
2. To protect crops and farmers.
3. To make measurement of all agricultural land and later make the tax policy. When unfertile land becomes under fertile, Shivaji Raje gave subsity to farmer for five years. The year by year implied the proper taxation. He declared hundred percentage subsidies

during drought time. In drought situation he imported grain from other kingdom and distributed to subject. For the irrigation Shivaji Raje spent lot of money on canals. Development.

Expenditure System:-

He spent major amount on administration. Each servant had given salary. Chief – Minister had given 15 thousands hon per year. Shivaji Raje had 208260 army men, and he spent on development of his army. He also spent hon for agricultural development. He built major and many dams, and built canals, for proper irrigation. He decided subsidy for agricultural development and decreased rate of interest.

Shivkalin Transaction:-

In the period of Shivkal, Gold, Silver, and bronze played. Important role in financial transaction The business based on 'HON'. 'Hon' was the currency of his time and 'Shivarai' was con at that times, the coins were manufactured by goldsmiths and Shavakar

Conclusion:-

1. At the time of Shivkal , agriculture was only one business for livelihood. Hence, Shivaji Maharaj had concentrated and took decision about welfare of Farmers, labors and developed agricultural area.
2. Shivaji Maharaj was developed business and trade, and imposed taxes according an ability of traders. Because of this policy, trade and business had developed and kingdom got more tax.
3. He provided protection to trade and business. This policy shows equality with German Economist Fedearal Least.
4. The taxation policy seems quality with Kautily's policy.
5. In Shivkalin Economy all income spent on development of kingdom and welfare of subject.
6. Shivaji Raje spent less amount for himself.
7. He protected fundamental rights of subject.

8. Along with Economical development, Shivaji Raje made social and cultural Development.

संदर्भ ग्रंथसुची

१. शिवकालीन महाराष्ट्र : अ.रा.कुलकर्णी राजहंस प्रकाशन प्रायव्हेट लि. ४ थी आवृत्ती २००९
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